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CORPORATE WELLNESS AND ORGANIZATIONAL COMMITMENT IN THE INDIAN IT SECTOR: AN EMPIRICAL ANALYSIS OF A CULTURE OF HEALTH

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ABSTRACT

Corporate wellness programmes, covering initiatives that support employees “physical, mental and social well-being, have become increasingly important in organizations. Organizational commitment, defined as employees’ emotional and intellectual attachment to the organization, remains a major predictor of performance, retention and long-term success. This study investigates the impact of corporate wellness programmes on organizational commitment in the information technology (IT) sector in Bengaluru, India. A cross-sectional survey was conducted with 340 IT professionals using a self-administered questionnaire. Data were analysed using EFA, CFA and SEM. EFA identified five dimensions of corporate wellness Health and Nutrition Programmes (HNP), Employee Support Programmes (ESP), Mental and Physical Health Initiatives (MPH), Workplace Conditions (WC) and Organizational Policy (OP) across 33 items. Organizational commitment was measured through 16 items loading on affective, normative and continuance components. KMO values of 0.862 (wellness) and 0.784 (commitment) confirmed sampling adequacy. CFA results showed acceptable model fit (e.g., CMIN/DF = 1.751; GFI = 0.906; CFI = 0.929; RMSEA = 0.061). The structural model also demonstrated strong fit (CMIN/DF = 2.893; GFI = 0.922; CFI = 0.972; RMSEA = 0.006), confirming a substantial positive effect of corporate wellness on organizational commitment. Findings emphasise that wellness-focused organizational cultures strengthen employee commitment and offer strategic value for human resource management.

KEYWORDS: Corporate Wellness, Organizational Commitment, Culture of Health, Information Technology, Employee Support Programmes.

1. INTRODUCTION

The contemporary workplace is undergoing profound transformation. Organizations increasingly recognise that employees are not merely “resources” but individuals with distinct needs, aspirations and vulnerabilities.

In knowledge-intensive and high-pressure sectors such as information technology (IT), questions of health, burnout, work–life balance and psychological well-being have become central to debates about sustainable organizational performance and social change in work. Within this broader transformation, corporate wellness programmes have emerged as a core element of organizational strategy. These programmes encompass a variety of initiatives designed to support physical health, mental well-being, lifestyle choices and social support at work. Organizational commitment, on the other hand, refers to workers' involvement, identity, and emotional tie to their company (Meyer and Allen 1991) continues to be a key predictor of performance, citizenship behaviours, retention and organizational stability (Lee 2023; Miško *et al.* 2021). The Indian corporate landscape, and particularly the IT industry, has been experiencing rapid growth, intense competition and changing labour market dynamics. Long working hours, tight project timelines and global client expectations can generate high job demands and stress. Against this background, wellness initiatives are not only a human resource tool but also part of a wider cultural shift towards acknowledging employee well-being as a central organizational value and as a dimension of social transformation in work and employment relations.

Organizations are progressively implementing health screenings, dietary counselling, mental health support, employee assistance programs, flexible work schedules, and other wellness initiatives in India's IT hubs, including Bengaluru. Such practices contribute to a “culture of health” (Payne *et al.* 2018), reshaping expectations about what a “good employer” looks like and how work should be organised to support human flourishing rather than burnout. Organizational commitment is especially significant in this environment. Highly skilled IT professionals often have multiple employment options; their continued attachment to a particular organization cannot be taken for granted. When employees perceive that their organization cares for their well-being and invests in wellness initiatives, they may reciprocate with stronger affective and normative commitment (Grawitch *et al.* 2007; Xiu *et*

al. 2019). On the other hand, cultures that normalize excessive effort and disregard wellbeing can weaken dedication and promote turnover. Thus, examining the connection between corporate wellness initiatives and organizational commitment in the Indian IT industry sheds light on how changing workplace and health-related cultural practices relate to more general processes of social change in employment relations, organizational norms, and employee expectations. The present study has two main aims. First, it assesses the impact of corporate wellness programmes on organizational commitment among IT professionals in Bengaluru. Second, it identifies which dimensions of corporate wellness are most salient in shaping commitment in this context. The study provides quantitative evidence from an under-researched context: wellness programmes and commitment in Indian IT organizations. Conceptually, it draws together organizational commitment theory, Social Exchange Theory, the Job Demands–Resources (JD–R) model, Self-Determination Theory (SDT), psychological contract theory and employee wellness models to articulate a framework linking corporate wellness as a cultural resource to employees' commitment.

1.1. Research Objectives

1. To identify and validate the key scopes of corporate wellness programmes and organizational commitment using Exploratory and Confirmatory Factor Analysis.
2. To evaluate the structural relationship between corporate wellness programmes and organizational commitment using Structural Equation Modelling.
3. To determine whether employees' perceptions of corporate wellness programmes significantly influence their levels of organizational commitment in the Indian IT sector.

2. THEORETICAL BACKGROUND AND LITERATURE REVIEW

2.1. Organizational Commitment

Meyer and Allen's (1991) three-component model remains one of the most influential frameworks for understanding organizational commitment. They distinguish affective commitment, continuance commitment and normative commitment.

High commitment is typically associated with positive work outcomes, including performance, extra-role behaviours, lower turnover intentions and stronger organizational citizenship (Massoud *et al.* 2020; Modise 2023). The current study adopts this tripartite conceptualisation and measures overall

commitment through items representing these three facets (Alam 2011).

2.2. Social Exchange Theory and the Psychological Contract

According to the Social Exchange Theory, relationships are based on mutual support and resource exchanges. When employees perceive that organizations invest in their well-being through wellness programmes, they may feel obliged to reciprocate with greater commitment and positive work behaviours (Peña et al. 2024).

Similarly, the idea of a psychological contract captures implicit expectations between employees and employers (Guest 2004). Wellness programmes can signal that the organization values employees holistically, not only as producers of output. This strengthens perceptions of a fair and supportive psychological contract, thereby enhancing loyalty and commitment (Miraglia and Johns 2015).

2.3. Job Demands–Resources Model and Self-Determination Theory

The JD–R model suggests that job demands (for example, workload, time pressure) and job resources jointly affect burnout, engagement and related outcomes (Taris et al. 2017; Rai and Gupta 2021). Corporate wellness initiatives can be conceptualised as job and personal resources which help employees cope with high demands, reduce strain and foster engagement and commitment. SDT places a strong emphasis on intrinsic motivation and the satisfaction of fundamental psychological demands for relatedness, competence, and autonomy (Deci and Ryan 2008). When wellness programmes allow employees to make meaningful choices about their health and provide supportive environments for well-being, they satisfy these needs, enhancing intrinsic motivation and, by extension, organizational commitment (Lee and Ashforth 1996; Richemond and Charles 2020).

2.4. Corporate Wellness as a Culture of Health

Recent work on workplace wellness stresses the importance of a culture of health, where health-supportive norms, policies and practices are embedded in everyday organizational life (Payne et al. 2018; Gubler and Pierce 2018). Such a culture can include HNP, mental health and stress-management initiatives, employee assistance and support services, supportive leadership behaviours, workplace design and conditions conducive to well-being, and policies that enable work–life balance and protect psychological safety. These initiatives do more than

change individual behaviours; they contribute to a broader cultural and social re-orientation of work, challenging older models that normalised overwork and neglect of health (Muñoz et al. 2023; Naz et al. 2020). In this sense, corporate wellness is not merely a set of benefits but a social practice that can reinforce or transform power relations, expectations and identities in organizations.

2.5. Research Model and Hypothesis

Building on these perspectives, this study conceptualises corporate wellness programmes as a multi-dimensional construct comprising

- Health and Nutrition Programmes (HNP)
- Employee Support Programmes (ESP)
- Mental and Physical Health Initiatives (MPH)
- Workplace Conditions (WC)
- Organisational Policy (OP)

Organisational commitment is measured through affective, normative and continuance commitment. The basic assumption, supported by prior studies on wellness and commitment (Grawitch et al. 2007; Peña et al. 2024; Muñoz et al. 2023), is that corporate wellness programmes have a positive and significant effect on employees' organisational assurance.

Accordingly, the following hypothesis is proposed

- H1: Corporate wellness programmes have a positive and significant effect on employees' organizational commitment.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Research Design and Context

In order to investigate the connection between corporate wellness initiatives and organizational commitment, the study used a cross-sectional survey design. The empirical context comprises IT organizations located in the Bengaluru region of India. This setting is characterized by intense competition, project-based work, and high job demands, making wellness and commitment particularly salient issues.

3.2. Sample and Data Collection

A self-administered online questionnaire disseminated via Google Forms was used to gather data from 340 working IT professionals. Potential respondents who worked for different IT companies in the Bengaluru area were contacted using simple random sampling. Informed consent was acquired prior to data collection, and participation was voluntary and anonymous. Confidentiality was guaranteed to respondents, and no sensitive or

identifiable personal data was recorded.

3.3 Measures

A structured questionnaire was developed based on prior literature on corporate wellness, organizational commitment, and related constructs. All items were measured on a five-point Likert scale ranging from 1 = "strongly agree" to 5 = "strongly disagree."

Corporate wellness programmes were measured using 33 items covering five dimensions: HNP, ESP, MPH, WC, and OP.

Organizational commitment was measured using 16 items representing affective, normative, and continuance commitment, drawing on Meyer and Allen's (1991) conceptualization and its subsequent applications (Alam 2011; Lee 2023).

3.4 Data Analysis Procedures

Data analysis was conducted using SPSS (version 26) and Structural Equation Modeling software. The analysis proceeded in several stages

1. Sampling Adequacy

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin tests were performed to determine the suitability of the data for factor analysis (Kaiser and Rice 1974; Hair et al. 2010).

2. Exploratory Factor Analysis

Principal Component Analysis with Varimax rotation was used to identify the underlying factor structure of both corporate wellness programmes and organizational commitment.

3. Confirmatory Factor Analysis

Separate CFAs were conducted for the wellness and commitment constructs to validate their measurement models.

4. Structural Equation Modeling

The hypothesized structural relationship between corporate wellness programmes and organizational commitment was tested and model fit evaluated.

Fit indices included the chi-square/degrees of freedom ratio, Goodness-of-Fit Index, Adjusted GFI, Tucker-Lewis Index, Comparative Fit Index, Root

Mean Square Error of Approximation, Parsimony-Normed Fit Index, Root Mean Square Residual, and Incremental Fit Index (Hair et al. 1998; Stone 2021).

4. RESULTS

4.1. KMO and Factorability

The KMO measure of sampling adequacy for corporate wellness programmes was 0.862, while for organizational commitment it was 0.784. Both values exceed the recommended threshold of 0.60, indicating that the data are suitable for factor analysis (Kaiser and Rice 1974; Hair et al. 2010).

The cumulative proportion of variance explained by the factors was 50.331% for corporate wellness programmes and 66.7% for organizational commitment. In social science research, cumulative variance around 50–60% is generally considered acceptable, particularly when dealing with complex psychological constructs (Hair et al. 2010).

4.2. Exploratory Factor Analysis

EFA was conducted using Principal Component Analysis with Varimax rotation.

For corporate wellness programmes, 33 items loaded on five factors with loadings of 0.517 and above.

The factors were labelled as HNP, ESP, MPH, WC and Organizational Policy (OP). For organizational commitment, 16 items loaded on three factors with loadings 0.587 and above, corresponding to affective commitment, normative commitment and continuance commitment. The multidimensional conceptualization of both constructs is supported by these findings.

4.3. Confirmatory Factor Analysis: Corporate Wellness Programmes

CFA was conducted to validate the five-factor measurement model of corporate wellness programmes. The model specified the 33 observed items loading on the five latent dimensions HNP, ESP, MPH, WC and OP.

Table 1. Model Fit Indices for Corporate Wellness Programmes.

Sl. No	Test Statistics examined	Values obtained	Inferences
1	CMIN/DF	1.751	Supported since CMIN/DF Value should be less than 3; RMSEA Value should be less than 0.08, Naz et al., 2020; Payne et al., 2018, PNFI should be >0.50, GFI; AGFI;TLI;CFI; IFI should be > 0.9, RMR should be <0.05 supported by the studies of Muñoz et al. (2023); Peña et al., 2024.
2	GFI	.906	
3	AGFI	.975	
4	TLI	.914	
5	CFI	.929	
6	RMSEA	.061	
7	PNFI	.625	
8	RMR	.049	
9	IFI	.932	

Figure 1: Measurement Model for Corporate Wellness Programmes.

The measurement model produced the following fit indices: CMIN/DF = 1.751, GFI = 0.906, AGFI = 0.975, TLI = 0.914, CFI = 0.929, RMSEA = 0.061, PNFI = 0.625, RMR = 0.049, IFI = 0.932. The corresponding measurement model for corporate wellness programmes is shown in Figure 1, and the detailed fit indices are reported in Table 1. All indices fall within acceptable threshold value, indicating that the proposed measurement model for corporate wellness programmes fits the data satisfactorily.

4.4. Confirmatory Factor Analysis: Organizational Commitment

A separate CFA was conducted for the organizational commitment construct, specifying 16 observed items loading on three factors: affective, normative and continuance commitment. The measurement model yielded the following fit indices: CMIN/DF = 1.921, GFI = 0.897, AGFI = 0.962, TLI = 0.977, CFI = 0.897, RMSEA = 0.068, PNFI = 0.682, RMR = 0.045, IFI = 0.899. The measurement model for organizational commitment is presented in Figure 2, and the associated fit indices are summarized in Table 2.

Figure 2: Measurement Model for Organizational Commitment.

Table 2: Model Fit Indices for Organizational Commitment.

Sl. No	Test Statistics examined	Values obtained	Inferences
1	CMIN/DF	1.921	Supported since CMIN/DF Value should be less than 3; RMSEA Value should be less than 0.08, Naz et al., 2020; Payne et al., 2018, PNFI should be >0.50, GFI; AGFI;TLI;CFI; IFI should be > 0.9, RMR should be <0.05 supported by the studies of Muñoz et al. (2023); Peña et al., 2024.
2	GFI	.897	
3	AGFI	.962	
4	TLI	.977	
5	CFI	.897	
6	RMSEA	.068	
7	PNFI	.682	
8	RMR	.045	
9	IFI	.899	

Most indices are close to or above recommended cut-off values, and the RMSEA is below 0.08,

suggesting that the three-factor model of organizational commitment is acceptable.

4.5. Structural Model: Relationship Between Corporate Wellness and Commitment

To test H1, a structural model was specified in which the latent construct Corporate Wellness Programmes predicts Organizational Commitment. The structural model reported the following fit indices: CMIN/DF = 2.893, GFI = 0.922, AGFI = 0.918, TLI = 0.981, CFI = 0.972, RMSEA = 0.006, PNFI = 0.639, RMR = 0.047, IFI = 0.998.

The overall structural model linking corporate wellness programmes and organizational commitment is depicted in Figure 3, while the model fit indices are reported in Table 3.

Figure 3: Structural Equation Model.

Table 3: Model Fit Indices for Structural Model.

Sl. No	Test Statistics examined	Values obtained	Inferences
1	CMIN/DF	2.893	Supported since CMIN/DF Value should be less than 3; RMSEA Value should be less than 0.08, Naz et al.,2020; Payne et al., 2018, PNFI should be >0.50, GFI; AGFI, TLI; CFI; IFI should be > 0.9, RMR should be <0.05, supported by the studies of Muñoz el al. (2023); Peña et al. (2024).
2	GFI	.922	
3	AGFI	.918	
4	TLI	.981	
5	CFI	.972	
6	RMSEA	.006	
7	PNFI	.639	
8	RMR	.047	
9	IFI	.998	

These values show that the structural model and the observed data generally fit well. The path from Corporate Wellness Programmes to Organizational Commitment was positive and statistically significant, supporting H1. In substantive terms, employees who perceive a stronger culture of health and more comprehensive wellness support report higher levels of organizational commitment.

5. DISCUSSION

5.1. Interpretation of Findings

The analysis demonstrates that corporate wellness programmes exert a significant positive influence on employees’ organizational commitment in the Indian IT sector. Each of the identified dimensions HNP,

ESP, MPH, WC and Organizational Policy contributes to a broader culture of well-being that strengthens employees' emotional ties, sense of obligation and perceived costs of leaving. As illustrated in Figure 3, the structural path from corporate wellness programmes to organizational commitment is positive and statistically significant, consistent with the strong model fit reported in Table 3.

The findings align with other studies that demonstrate how wellness programs can improve commitment, engagement, and job satisfaction (Grawitch et al. 2007; Muñoz et al. 2023; Peña et al. 2024). According to Social Exchange Theory and psychological contract perspectives, the results support the notion that when companies offer health resources, psychological support, and favorable working conditions, employees respond with more dedication (Guest 2004; Miraglia and Johns 2015). The robustness of the five wellness dimensions and the three-component commitment structure is also supported by the CFA results in Figures 1 and 2 and the fit indices in Tables 1 and 2.

From a JD-R lens, wellness programmes function as resources that mitigate the adverse effects of high job demands common in IT work (Taris et al. 2017). MPH and ESP may reduce burnout and stress, while supportive policies and conducive working conditions encourage sustained engagement. SDT provides a complementary explanation: wellness initiatives that respect employees' autonomy and support competence and relatedness are likely to foster intrinsic motivation and positive attitudes towards the organization (Deci and Ryan 2008).

5.2. Cultural and Social-Change Implications

Beyond the individual and organizational outcomes, the results speak to broader cultural and social changes in the organisation of work in India's IT sector. The move from seeing employees solely as performers of tasks to recognising them as whole persons with health, family and psychological needs reflects a shift in organizational values and cultural norms. Corporate wellness initiatives signal an emerging ethic of care in corporate practices, even within highly competitive markets.

By investing in wellness, organizations in Bengaluru and similar hubs contribute to reshaping expectations around what constitutes a "good job" and a "responsible employer". For employees, this can translate into new forms of identity and belonging, where being part of an organization that visibly values health and well-being become a source of pride and commitment (Naz et al. 2020; Paulino

2023). At a broader societal level, these developments intersect with debates on sustainable work, mental health awareness and the redistribution of responsibility for well-being between individuals, organizations and the state. In this way, corporate wellness programmes participate in ongoing processes of social transformation in contemporary working lives.

5.3. Practical Implications

For practitioners, the study suggests several implications. First, corporate wellness should be approached as an integrated system encompassing health and nutrition, mental health support, employee assistance, physical work environment and supportive policies, rather than as a set of isolated activities. Second, leaders and managers need to model healthy behaviours and visibly support wellness initiatives so that they become part of everyday organizational culture, not peripheral benefits. Third, HR strategies should explicitly recognise corporate wellness as a lever for enhancing affective and normative commitment, which in turn influences retention, citizenship behaviours and performance. Finally, in the Indian IT sector, wellness initiatives may need to respond to specific cultural expectations, work patterns, family structures and social norms around mental health, work-life balance and gender roles.

6. LIMITATIONS AND FUTURE RESEARCH

There are a number of limitations to the study that provide opportunities for future investigation. Causal inference is limited by the cross-sectional nature of the data. The evolution of wellness activities and dedication may be better captured by longitudinal investigations.

The sample is restricted to IT professionals in Bengaluru. Future research could extend the analysis to other regions in India and to different industries to compare how sectoral and regional cultures shape the wellness-commitment relationship.

The study focuses on overall organizational commitment as the outcome. Future work might examine other outcomes of corporate wellness programmes, such as employee engagement, productivity, absenteeism, presenteeism, innovation or organizational citizenship behaviours (Payne et al. 2018; Gubler and Pierce 2018).

Finally, qualitative research could deepen understanding of how employees interpret wellness practices, how these intersect with issues of gender, class or family responsibilities, and how they contribute to wider social debates about "good

work” and corporate responsibility.

7. CONCLUSION

In a demanding and rapidly changing work environment, especially in sectors such as IT, questions of employee well-being and commitment are central to both organizational sustainability and broader social debates about work. This study demonstrates that employees’ organizational commitment in the Indian IT sector is significantly improved by corporate wellness programs that are designed as a multifaceted system of activities and regulations.

By fostering a culture of health through HNP, employee support mechanisms, MPH, supportive WC and inclusive organizational policies, employers can strengthen affective, normative and continuance commitment. In doing so, they not only secure performance and retention benefits but also participate in wider processes of cultural and social change that redefine how work is experienced and valued.

For organisations aspiring to be both competitive and socially responsible, investment in carefully designed and genuinely implemented wellness programmes emerges as a strategic and ethical imperative.

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